

**SYNTHESIS OF COPPER COMPLEXES OF SCHIFF BASE LIGANDS CONTAINING
NITROGEN, OXYGEN AND SULPHUR DONOR ATOMS AND THEIR
SPECTROSCOPIC CHARACTERIZATION**

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ABSTRACT

Cu (II) complexes are synthesized with 2 ligands, pyridine-2-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone and pyridine-2-carboxyaldehydesemicarbazone respectively. These complexes have been characterized on the basis of their elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility and electronic, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance and Mass spectroscopic studies. The complexes in DMSO have been found to possess molar conductance between 5-10 $\Omega^{-1} \text{Cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ with Ligand 1 and between 130-185 for ligand 2, indicating their nonelectrolytic and 1:2 electrolytic nature respectively. Ligand 1 (Pyridine-2-carboxyaldehydethiosemicarbazone) has been found to be bidentate on the basis of IR spectral studies and thus the complexes with it have been formulated as $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{X}_2]$. Ligand 2 (Pyridine-2-carboxyaldehydesemicarbazone) is found to be tridentate, and complexes with it, can be formulated as $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{X}_2]$. Where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{SCN}^-, \text{ClO}_4^-$. Spectroscopic studies have revealed tetragonal geometry for all the complexes and paramagnetic nature with one unpaired electron.

KEYWORDS: Copper (II) complexes, Spectroscopic studies, Thiosemicarbazone and semicarbazone.

INTRODUCTION

The thiosemicarbazones and semicarbazones of general formula $\text{RCH}=\text{N}-\text{NHC}(\text{NH}_2)=\text{S}$ and $\text{RCH}=\text{N}-\text{NHC}(\text{NH}_2)=\text{O}$ respectively have always been matter of attraction for the chemists due to their ability to show variable coordinating ability and to form different kinds of complexes by coordinating through various atoms and showing different kinds of geometry^[1], that gives them distinctive capability^[2] of trapping metal ions and also donating electron pairs to metal ions.^[3] This further makes them special from the point of pharmaceutical properties^[4] ^[5] antimalarial antibacterial^[6] anti fungal properties as well as antioxidant activities.^[7] The thiosemicarbazones have caused tumor cell death by the bringing about change in the geometry,^[8] point of attachment and other conditions.^[9] They have also been found to show catalytic activities in various reactions. Researches have also conducted and found positive result for anti-corrosion activities by them against strong acids.^[10] As well as the quantum mechanical and computational studies are also being conducted on these kinds of compounds.^[11]

The present paper discusses the synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of Copper metal complexes of Chloride, Bromide, Perchlorate and

Thiocyanate of Pyridine-2-carboxyaldehydethiosemicarbazone and Pyridine-2-carboxyaldehydesemicarbazone as ligand.^[12]

EXPERIMENTAL

Material-All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and procured from Sigma Aldrich and used as received.

Synthesis of ligand 1- (Pyridine-2-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone)

The general method of preparation have been employed. 20 ml ethyl alcohol and 0.91 g (0.01 mole) of thiosemicarbazide taken in a Round bottom flask and heated at constant temperature for 1 hour. Also 2-formyl pyridine aldehyde (0.95 ml) with minimum amount of ethanol is heated and refluxed simultaneously in separate flask. Solutions from both the flasks is mixed with constant stirring and refluxed for 8 hours and cooled in ice bath overnight. Off white or pale yellow coloured ligand is filtered out, washed and dried on vacuum.^{[13][14]}

Figure 1: Reaction Scheme for ligand 1.

Synthesis of ligand 2 (Pyridine-2-carboxaldehydesemicarbazone)

1.115 gm(0.01mole)of semicarbazide hydrochloride, and 0.82 gm(0.01mole)of sodium acetate, separately being dissolved in distilled water and mixed in already reflux

heated solution of 0.95 ml (0.01 mole)Pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde in ethanol with constant and vigorous stirring and maintaining temperature below 5⁰C. Off white shining precipitate is filtered out, washed and dried on vacuum.^[14]

Figure 2: Reaction scheme for ligand 2.

Synthesis of complexes

0.002 mole(0.36g)of ligand (2:1) dissolved in minimum amount of hot ethanolic solution is mixed with 0.001 mole heated ethanolic solution of respective metal salts of Copper. The mixture is refluxed for 6-7 hours at a constant temperature. The mixture is cooled on ice bath and left overnight. Precipitate filtered out, washed and dried under vacuum. Purity of complex was checked with TLC and melting point was determined.

Physical Measurement

With Carlo Erba elemental analyser, the C,H and N content were determined. Magnetic susceptibility has been measured on Gouy Balance, using CuSO₄. 5H₂O as calibrant. Molar conductance was measured on systronic conductivity meter model 304. Mass spectrum has been recorded on JEOL, JMS, DX 303 mass spectrometer. ¹H-NMR spectra of ligand was recorded on Bruker Advance Ultrashield-500 spectrometer using CDCl₃ as the solvent. IR spectra was recorded on FTIR BX-II spectrophotometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ligand

1-(Pyridine-2-

carboxaldehydethiosemicarbazone)

The ligand is stable at room temperature with high melting point. In the IR spectra the bands around 3347 cm⁻¹ and 3200 cm⁻¹, can be attributed to NH₂ and NH groups respectively. Band at 3116 cm⁻¹ and 2975 cm⁻¹ are due to C-H str vibrations. The C=S, pyridine C=N and azomethine HC=N can be correlated to bands at 1261 cm⁻¹, 698 cm⁻¹ and 1626 cm⁻¹ respectively. Mass spectrum shows peak at 179 corresponding to (M⁺).

NMR spectrum of ligand shows the following peaks, δ 8.19(d,1H,C(4)H), 8.042(t,1H,C(3)H), 11.82(s,1H,N(3)H) 7.59(m,1H,C(2)H) 8.446(s,1H,N(4)H), 7.88(s,1H,C(6)H), 7.79(d,1H,C(1)H),

Figure 3: IR spectrum of Ligand 1(Pyridine-2-carboxaldehydethiosemicarbazone).

Figure 4: NMR spectrum of Ligand 1(Pyridine-2-carboxaldehydethiosemicarbazone).

Ligand 2-(Pyridine-2-carboxaldehydesemicarbazone)
The IR spectrum of ligand 2 also gives peak at 3445 cm⁻¹, 3405 cm⁻¹ corresponding to NH₂ and NH groups, peak at 3046 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C-H str, 1659 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=O (carbonyl group), 1481 cm⁻¹ corresponding to azomethine CH=N and at 708 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=N(pyridine) bonds. Mass spectrum shows peak at 163 amu corresponding to (M⁺).

NMR spectrum with the following peaks can further support the proposed structure

δ 10.53(s,1H,N(3)H), 8.83(s,1H,C(6)H),
8.24(s,1H,N(4)H), 7.53(d,1H,C(4)H),
8.14(d,1H,C(1)H),8.00(t,1H,C(2)H), 7.84(s,1H,C(3)H).

Figure 5: IR spectrum of Ligand 2(Pyridine-2-carboxyaldehydesemicarbazone).

Figure 6: NMR spectrum of Ligand 2(Pyridine-2-carboxyaldehydesemicarbazone).

Complexes - The elemental analysis and physical measurement values of the ligand and complexes predicts the formula as mentioned in Table 1. The complexes have been found to be soluble in either DMSO or DMF and sparingly soluble in water and ethanol.

The value of molar conductance of the complexes with ligand 1, in DMSO lie in the range of 5-10 $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$ showing all the complexes to be a non-electrolyte and

with ligand 2 lies in the range of 130-185 $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$ showing its 1:2 electrolytic nature.^[16]

Interpretation of IR spectra

IR bands provide very important information about the bonding in the complexes. The peaks at 3347 cm^{-1} , 3200 cm^{-1} corresponding to NH_2 and NH groups, at 3116 cm^{-1} corresponding to C-H str and at 1261 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=S in ligand 1 do not show much displacement on complexation, indicating their non involvement in

bonding to metal. While band at 1626 cm^{-1} and 698 cm^{-1} show appreciable displacement indicating the bonding of azomethine and pyridine N with metal, which strengthens or weakens the bonds resulting in their shift in the IR spectrum of complexes. Thus ligand 1 is supposed to be bidentate in nature.

The ligand 2 shows two bands at 3445 cm^{-1} and 3405 cm^{-1} corresponding to NH_2 and NH groups which are not displaced much in the complexes indicating their non involvement in bonding to metal. The bands at 708 cm^{-1} , 1659 cm^{-1} and 1481 cm^{-1} showing downward and upward shift in complexes indicate the involvement of pyridine nitrogen, azomethine nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen respectively in coordination with metal in complexes. Rest of the bands do not show only minimum shift showing the tridentate nature of ligand.^[17]

Electronic spectra of complexes

Electronic spectra gives three bands in the region 10110-13121, 16278-18270 and 21830-27630 corresponding to ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$, ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ transitions, supporting the tetragonal geometry for the complexes due to Jahn Teller Distortion.

The magnetic moment values lie in the range of 1.89-2.01 B.M., showing their paramagnetic nature with one unpaired electron as expected.^[1]

Table 1: Analytical data of ligands and complexes.

Sl. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Colour	M.P. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis %found(calculated)			
							Cu	C	H	N
1	PATS	C ₇ H ₈ N ₄ S	180	White	179	68	-	46.60 (46.65)	4.30 (4.47)	30.2 (31.09)
2	PASC	C ₇ H ₈ N ₄ O	164	Off white	129	62	-	50.11 (51.21)	4.48 (4.91)	34.0 (34.13)
3	[Cu(PATS) ₂ Cl ₂]	CuC ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₈ S ₂ Cl ₂	495	Dark green	213	54	12.80 (12.84)	33.68 (33.98)	3.21 (3.26)	22.40 (23.64)
4	[Cu(PATS) ₂ Br ₂]	CuC ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₈ S ₂ Br ₂	584	Black	230	62	10.81 (10.88)	27.89 (28.80)	2.72 (2.76)	19.10 (19.19)
5	[Cu(PATS) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	CuC ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₁₀ S ₄	539	Brown	234	58	11.70 (11.76)	35.48 (35.58)	2.90 (2.99)	25.90 (25.93)
6	[Cu(PATS) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	CuC ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₈ S ₂ Cl ₂ O ₈	623	Greenish black	245	63	10.10 (10.20)	25.86 (26.99)	2.47 (2.59)	17.70 (17.99)
7	[Cu(PASC) ₂]Cl ₂	CuC ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	463	Creamish green	228	64	13.59 (13.73)	35.98 (36.33)	3.32 (3.48)	24.10 (24.21)
8	[Cu(PASC) ₂] Br ₂	CuC ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₂ Br ₂	551.7	Light brown	234	65	11.20 (11.52)	30.21 (30.48)	2.34 (2.92)	20.12 (20.31)
9	[Cu(PASC) ₂](SCN) ₂	CuC ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₁₀ S ₂ O ₂	508	Brown	232	56	12.26 (12.51)	37.24 (37.83)	2.98 (3.17)	27.52 (27.57)
10	[Cu(PASC) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	CuC ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₈ Cl ₂ O ₁₀	589	Dark green	241	57	10.58 (10.76)	28.32 (28.46)	2.52 (2.73)	18.61 (18.97)

Table 2: IR spectral data of ligands and complexes.

Compounds	N-H (cm ⁻¹)	C-H (cm ⁻¹)	C=O (cm ⁻¹)	C=S (cm ⁻¹)	CH=N (cm ⁻¹)	C=N Aromatic (cm ⁻¹)
PATS	3347,3200	3116,2975	-	1261	1626	698
PASC	3445,3405	3046	1659	-	1481	708
[Cu(PATS) ₂ Cl ₂]	3349	3110	-	1259	1618	709
[Cu(PATS) ₂ Br ₂]	3350	3099	-	1256	1613	711
[Cu(PATS) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	3347	3118	-	1262	1611	709
[Cu(PATS) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	3340	3112	-	1263	1616	724
[Cu(PASC) ₂]Cl ₂	3439	3047	1648	-	1464	718
[Cu(PASC) ₂]Br ₂	3437	3042	1647	-	1461	720
[Cu(PASC) ₂](SCN) ₂	3431	3043	1650	-	1468	722
[Cu(PASC) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	3442	3038	1642	-	1470	727

Table 3: Physical properties of complexes and electronic spectral data.

Complexes	Molar conductance Ω ⁻¹ Cm ² mol ⁻¹	Magnetic moment μ _{eff} (B.M.)	Electronic spectral data (λ _{max} in cm ⁻¹)		
[Cu(L ¹) ₂ Cl ₂]	10	2.0	10312	16328	21830
[Cu(L ¹) ₂ Br ₂]	6	1.89	13121	17290	23490
[Cu(L ¹) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	7	1.9	12323	16278	27340
[Cu(L ¹) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	5	2.01	10110	18270	22350
[Cu(L ²) ₂]Cl ₂	185	1.99	11102	18234	23231
[Cu(L ²) ₂]Br ₂	166	2.01	10137	17560	22270
[Cu(L ²) ₂](SCN) ₂	174	1.97	10290	16280	27630
[Cu(L ²) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	130	1.98	11920	16590	23476

CONCLUSION

On the basis of elemental analysis data and spectral analysis, the complexes with ligand 1 and ligand 2 have been found to possess the formula as shown in Table 1. IR spectral data suggest bidentate nature of ligand 1 and tridentate nature of ligand 2. According to the molar conductance data and electronic spectral studies ligand 1 complexes have been proposed to be nonelectrolyte with tetragonal geometry while complexes with ligand 2 are found to be 1:2 electrolyte having tetragonal geometry and according to the magnetic susceptibility values all the complexes are having Para magnetism with one unpaired electron.

Thus, the proposed structures of complexes with ligand 1 and ligand 2 are as follows-

Figure 7: Proposed structure of complexes with ligand 1 (Pyridine-2-carboxyaldehydethiosemicarbazone), Showing the

tetragonal geometry and non electrolytic nature.

Figure 8: Proposed structure of complexes with ligand 2 (Pyridine-2-carboxyaldehydesemicarbazone), Showing the tetragonal geometry and 1:2 electrolytic nature.

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